

Title: Firm Size and Economic Growth of Nigeria

Authors: Obasi, John Ogonnia & Osegbue, Francis Ifeanyi

Affiliation: ANAN University, Kwall. Plateau State of Nigeria & Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Anambra State of Nigeria

Journal Name: *AE-FUNAI Journal of Accounting, Business And Finance (FJABAF)*

Volume/ Issue / Page: Volume 9, Issue 1, Page 65-77

Year of publication: 2023

FIRM SIZE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH OF NIGERIA

OBASI, JOHN OGBONNIA

ANAN University, Kwall. Plateau State of Nigeria
Email:obasi.john@ananuniversity.edu.ng

OSEGBUE, FRANCIS IFEANYI

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Anambra State of Nigeria

ABSTRACT

the study is to determine the effect of total asset, firm age, profitability, and sales on economic growth. The study applied ex-post-facto research design. The population of the study is non financial firms listed in Nigeria Exchange Group. The sample size is Dangote group with emphasis on Sugar factory. Simple linear regression analysis was used which recognized Vector Auto regression [VAR] models. The study discovered that firm size granger causes economic growth. The study recommends that investors, investment managers and researchers should use total assets, firm age, profitability and sales to ascertain the extent to which firm size drives economic growth in Nigeria.

Key Words: Economic Growth, Firm age, Profitability

Introduction.

Among the economic progress in a country, one can be reflected by the capital market activity in that economy. As an emerging market in a given economy, the capital market's stock price movement determines changes in investors' interest in the stock price vis-à-vis economic growth. The higher the demand for stock, the higher the price and vice versa. [Sugosha and Artini 2020]. Firm size is related to firm value and firm value revolves around the extent of its investment. Firm size is the result of total assets, sales, profitability, firm age and such like, to show the ability of the issuer. The firm's level of profit making can affect the value of the firm. If her profitability is good, then investors, creditors and suppliers will begin to look into their strength, in getting profits from performance, sales and investment. [Chub and Andrian 2018].

The stock index as regards investment helps investors to know the performance of the company. The index of manufacturing firms has not been able to show excellent performance. This index contains those

that issue raw materials into finished/semi-finished products. This index can be reasonably corrected to date. The manufacturing sector index which are none financial consists of three main sectors, namely; the

AE-FUNAI Journal of Accounting Business and Finance (FJABAF)

chemical industry sector, various industries, the basics and consumer goods sector. In this concerned index, several stocks showed progressive agenda of the majority of the listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Does firm size affect the value of a corporation with profitability as intervening variable and gross domestic product as a moderating variable? The reason of the researcher to take a look into manufacturing companies is because they are one of the supporting sectors of the Nigerian economy. Researchers like Audretch and Elston [2000] found out that liquidity constraints affect firm size to a reasonable extent. Constraints in liquidity position of a firm can lead to credit rationing on the side of borrowers. (Jeff and Russel [1976] in Audretch and Elston [2000]) Recent papers have discovered that liquidity constraints tend to have a greater impact on smaller firms than larger ones. This is backed up by American research paper FHP [1988]. Unlike Germany where smaller firms enjoy lending rate due to effect of strong local and regional bank networks that target the growth of small and medium firms, it is not so in Nigeria's context, where our economy is being stagnated. Firm size, is it significant in determining economic growth of Nigeria?

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of firm size on economic growth of Nigeria. While the specific objectives include;

To determine the effect of total assets on economic growth of Nigeria.

To ascertain the effect of firm age on economic growth of Nigeria.

To determine the effect of profitability on economic growth of Nigeria.

To ascertain the effect of sales on economic growth of Nigeria **Research questions**

To what extent does total assets affect economic growth of Nigeria?

How far does firm age affect economic growth of Nigeria?

To what extent does profitability affect economic growth of Nigeria? Sales, does it actually affect economic growth of Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

A set of null hypotheses were formulated for this study. They are as follows

Total assets does not significantly affect economic growth of Nigeria;

Firm age does not significantly affect economic growth of Nigeria

Profitability does not significantly affect economic growth of Nigeria

Sales does not significantly affect economic growth of Nigeria

Significance of the study

This research work will benefit researchers, firm managers, stake holders and the government of the day. To address this gaps in firm size and economic growth, a sample of seventy, high trading nonfinancial quoted companies in Nigeria exchange group from 2017-2020 is used.

Three empirical techniques-pooled ordinary least squares [POLS] random effects [RE] and fixed effects [FE] are applied. The set of empirical analyses examine whether total assets, company's age, profitability and sales are effective in mitigating economic growth. All data are directly taken from companies financial statements. The rest of the study is structured as follows; section 2 reviews relevant literature, section 3 outlines the empirical approach and data, section 4 discusses the results while section 5 concludes the study.

Review of related literature Introduction.

Kitov [2011] defines firm size as total sales and the number of employees. It means the scale or volume of operation turned out by a single firm. It is determined by entrepreneurial skill, management ability, and availability of finance, availability of labor, nature of business and extent of the market.

Theory of Tobin Q on firm investment and cash flow measures the main factor that determines or affects the nature of the outcome of corporate optimal investment [determinants]. This theory summarizes relevant information about a firm's expected future profitability and financing condition. We investigate the extent to which firm size captures wrong measurement of real investment opportunities and financial position of a firm. If a firm's financial status is captured by a firm's size, then we would expect the size effect of firms which have financial constraints differ from those that are not financially constrained in their activities. This measure is analyzed using the following financial constraints theories ;(Kaplanzingale's theory [1997] ,the White Wu's theory [2006] of Hennessey [2005] and Headlock-Pierce theory [2010] of Rajesh [2020]). Kaplan zingale's financial measurement theory shows that corporate governance is the main reason for values of cash holdings of state owned enterprises [SOEs] being lower than those of private firms. According to them, values of cash holdings of SOEs are controlled by the central governments. The observation is because, central government control of SOEs have better governance and investment opportunities compared with the local government controlled ones. While Wu measurement theory asserts that firms that anticipate collateral constraints experience a side benefit from investing as capital invested helps to relax future constraints. Headlock-Piece theory states that higher earnings quality reduces dividends during crises period for group –affiliated firms. We anchor our work on Kaplan Zingale's theory.

Empirical review

Effect of total assets on economic growth.

Hashim, Gulzar and Naz [2020], conducted a test on whether firm size has significant impact on board structure vis-à-vis total assets. In their results no research has provided any specific reason to use a specific measure of firm size for a specific variable. As a result, different measures of firm size have yielded different results. According to them, increase in size of firm leads to increase in total assets of that firm. They used return on asset [R.O.A] and return on equity [R.O.E] as measures of performance. It is noteworthy that the level of a firm's performance determines her growth in total assets. This is supported by Dang, Li and Yang [2018]. In her empirical review, Thesai [2012] said that firm size has a positive effect on firm's financial performance. She used R.O.A to proxy performance. This in turn grows the total assets of a firm since total assets include cash, accounts receivable [money owed to the firm, inventory, equipment, tools etc]

Effect of firm age on economic growth

Loderer and Waelich [2010] and Akben-Seluck [2016] in their empirical tests discovered that younger firms earn a higher profit than older firms; but as they grow older, they begin to earn more profit than younger competitors. This means that firm age has significant positive relationship with profitability. But there is still a gap that should be researched on. Their researches covered between 2008 and 2016. Papadogonas [2007], Akinyomi and Olagaju [2012] studied whether larger firms out- perform smaller firms or vice versa. They reported a positive relationship between age and firm performance. While, Mazumder [1992]. Load, Segaira and Teruel [2013], Dogan, [2013] in their studies tests show a negative relationship. There is a gap of disagreement between their literature on firm size and performance. The proxies for measuring performance in their research include, return on assets [ROA], return on capital employed [ROCE], return on equity [ROE], profit margin and gross profit.

Ghafoorifard, Sheykh, Shakibae and Joshaghan [2014] used 96 listed companies on Tehran stock exchange to check whether the older a firm, the better its performance. The study includes those of Osusan, Nowak, Mbonga, Pule, Kibirige and Bilirywo [2015] and Kipesha [2013]. They demonstrate a positive relationship in Tanzania and Uganda. They used micro finance institution to effect this.

Effect of profitability on economic growth

Firm size, according to fixed effect model is positively related to profitability measure of return on assets. Prasetyatoko and Parmono [2009], examined the effect of firm size on performance considering pre- and

post-crises periods in Indonesia using 238 quoted firms between 1994 and 2007. In their result, there is a significant and positive relationship between total asset and return on assets in both pre- and post- crisis periods but size and market value have negative relationship. In another study, Pervan and Visic [2012] from 2002 to 2010, analyzed the impact of firms' total assets on return on assets performance in Croatia. They used fixed effects regression. They revealed that size of a firm, firms' total asset's natural logarithm and return on assets influences, are significant and positively related.

Mule, Mukas and Nzioka [2015] investigated size-performance linkage for 53 listed firms in Nairobi security exchange from 2010- 2014. They employed random effects GLS estimators. They found out that firm size [being determined by volume of sale or sales being its natural logarithm] is positively and significantly related only on ROE regression while insignificant in ROA and Tobin's Q regressions. The exploration of the determinants of firm's profitability of 31 private firms from 2004-2011 in EU-15 areas by Pattitoni, Petracci and Spisni [2014] concludes that firm size positively affects profitability. They used regression analysis .Most times, larger firms tend to have higher profitability than smaller firms due to non-linearity in size-profitability association. Dogan [2013], employed 200 listed firms in Borsa Istanbul between 2008-2011 and investigated the relationship between firm size indicators viz; total assets, total sales, number of employees, and firm performance with ROA. In Sri lanka, Niresh and Velnapy [2014] studied the relationship of size-profitability of 15 being represented by ROA. The results shows that each measure of size affects ROA of firms. This means that indicators are positively and significantly associated with listed manufacturing industries. They employed total assets and total sales as firm size indicators, net profit and return on asset as firms' profitability indicators. Using regression method of analysis, they discovered that there is no relationship between size and profitability indicators. In their empirical study on determinants of profitability, Ayturk and Yanik [2015] sampled 1.123 small and medium-sized enterprises [SEs] in Turkey between 2009 and 2013 using dynamic panel data to do their regression analyses. They discovered that although the influence of total sales on gross profit when divided by total assets is significantly negative, while ratio of profit before tax and interest to total assets are positively and significantly related and are affected by firm size indicators.

Ehi-Oshio, Adeyemi and Enofe [2013] empirically investigated the impact of firm attributes on corporate profitability on developing economies. They used ordinary least square method of regression to do their analysis. The study found positive relationship among the independent and dependent variables of the 40 sampled companies. Firm size is positively related with finance and profitability

Charles, Nma and Joshua in Abubakar [2021],examined the effect of firm characteristics on profitability of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria using multiple regression analytical tool with a population of 22 listed firms from 2011-2016. They found out that firm size, sales, growth and leverage have significant effects on profitability. But firm size and liquidity are not significantly related with profitability of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. The study recommended that Nigerian consumer goods should be carefully evaluated. Also, firm's characteristics [firm size, sales, growth and leverage] which affect the profits of the company should be considered before making major business decisions. This will help to improve their profitability

Akinyomi and Olagunju [2013] examined the effect of firm size on profitability of Nigerian manufacturing sector. They employed panel data that covered 2005-2012. They proxied profitability with return on assets and firm size with total assets whereas control variables were liquidity and leverage and the ratio of inventories. Their study revealed that firm size in terms of total assets and total sales has a positive effect on profitability. Coming to control variables, firm size has a negative relationship with inventory but a positive relationship with others.

Johnson [2007] in his study of size-profitability relationship used a sample of 250 Icelandic firms. He reported that firm size has negative but no statistical significant effect on profitability. Amato and Burson [2007] in their test of size-profit relationship for firms operating in the financial services sector in relation to the linear and cubic form of the relationship, they found out that firm size has negative influence on profitability which was not statistically significant. This result was on linear form. But cubic wise, firm size has positive relationship with ROA. Papadognas [2007] investigated size-profit relationship on a sample of 3035 Greek manufacturing firms for the period 1995-1999. He applied regression analytical technique and came up with the result that for all size classes, firms' profitability is positively influenced by firm size. Serrasqueiro and Nunes [2008] tested the relationship between firm size and performance

of small and medium sized Portuguese companies covering 1990-2003. Their results show that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between size and profitability of SMEs . For the Portuguese companies, there was statistically insignificant relationship between size and profitability. Lee [2009] in his study examined the role that firm size plays in profitability. He applied fixed effect panel data model and analyzed a sample of more than 7000 U.S. publicly held firms.

The results indicated that firm size plays an important role in explaining profitability. The relationship was nonlinear. This means that gains in profitability reduced for larger firms.

Effect of sales on economic growth

Thomas, Henry, Erika and Albert [2022] examined the impact of sales growth on firm value using return on asset as a moderating variable. They used regression analytical technique. Their results show that sales growth have negative impact and not significant to firm value. Total assets have significant impact and not significant on firm. They advise investors to be careful and not to invest on the basis of sales, growth and firm size as this may be misleading.

Talha, Muhammad, Hamza and Abdul [2021], studied the impact of firm size on profitability, using Top 10 cement companies in Pakistan. They used Panel data and multiple regression model on return on assets and return on equity together with total assets and total sales. The results show that total sales has positive impact on return on assets and return on equity when determined by total sales but when determined by total assets value, it has a negative impact.

Dogan [2013] in his study on impact of firm size found out that total assets have a significantly positive influence on profitability. Pervan and Visic [2012] evaluated the influence of firm size on profitability.

Niresh and Veinapy [2014] studied firm size and profitability. Their results show a weak firm size.

There is a weak relationship between firm size and profitability

3.5 Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Models

The VAR model is a multi-equation system where all the variables are treated as endogenous. There is thus one equation for each variable as dependent variable. Each equation has lagged values of all the included variables as dependent variables, including the dependent variable itself. Since there are no contemporaneous variables included as explanatory, right-hand side variables, the model is a reduced form. Thus all the equations have the same form since they share the same right-hand side variables.

Say the VAR model will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{lngdp}_t &= \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \text{lngdp}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j \text{lnrev}_{t-j} + \sum_{l=1}^k \phi_l \text{lnprof}_{t-l} + \sum_{m=1}^k \omega_m \text{lnata}_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^k \delta_n \text{lnfa}_{t-n} + \mu_{1t} \\
 \text{lnrev}_t &= \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \text{lngdp}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j \text{lnrev}_{t-j} + \sum_{l=1}^k \phi_l \text{lnprof}_{t-l} + \sum_{m=1}^k \omega_m \text{lnata}_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^k \delta_n \text{lnfa}_{t-n} + \mu_{2t} \\
 \text{lnprof}_t &= \rho + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \text{lngdp}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j \text{lnrev}_{t-j} + \sum_{l=1}^k \phi_l \text{lnprof}_{t-l} + \sum_{m=1}^k \omega_m \text{lnata}_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^k \delta_n \text{lnfa}_{t-n} + \mu_{3t} \\
 \text{lnata}_t &= \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \text{lngdp}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j \text{lnrev}_{t-j} + \sum_{l=1}^k \phi_l \text{lnprof}_{t-l} + \sum_{m=1}^k \omega_m \text{lnata}_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^k \delta_n \text{lnfa}_{t-n} + \mu_{4t} \\
 \text{lnfa}_t &= \delta + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \text{lngdp}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma_j \text{lnrev}_{t-j} + \sum_{l=1}^k \phi_l \text{lnprof}_{t-l} + \sum_{m=1}^k \omega_m \text{lnata}_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^k \delta_n \text{lnfa}_{t-n} + \mu_{5t}
 \end{aligned}$$

The endogenous variable *gdp* is also the explanatory variable in lagged form. How many lags become an empirical matter, which is decided at the estimation stage. where

- k = optimal lag length
- α, ρ, δ = intercepts
- $\beta_i, \gamma_j, \phi_l, \omega_m, \delta_n$ = short run dynamic of the coefficient of the model
- μ_{it} = residuals in the equation

Empirical Analysis Unit Root Test

The paper conducts unit root tests of the variables with Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF). Outcomes of the tests are presented in Table 4.1. According to the ADF test, all variables lngdp, lnrev, lnprof, lnta, lnfa accept null hypotheses at the 5 per cent level that they are level and not stationary, while the first log difference dlngdp, dlnrev, dlnprof, dlnta, dlnta reject the null hypotheses at the 5 per cent level that they are level and stationary. In conclusion, there is evidence that all variables except dlngdp, dlnrev, dlnprof, dlnta and dlnta appear to be I (1) processes

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test Using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Tests: 2006 - 2020.

Variable		ADF test stat	Critical Values			Order of integration
			1%	5%	10%	
Lngdp	Levels	-2.085**	-2.764	-1.812	-1.372	I (1)
	First diff	-2.338	-2.821	-1.833	-1.383	I (1)
Lnrev	Levels	-0.639	-2.764	-1.812	-1.372	I (1)
	First diff	-5.148**	-2.821	-1.833	-1.383	I (1)
lnprof	Levels	-0.691	-2.764	-1.812	-1.372	I (1)
	First diff	-3.509	-2.821	-1.833	-1.383	I (1)
Lnta	Levels	0.148	-2.764	-1.812	-1.372	I (1)
	First diff	-5.071*	-2.821	-1.833	-1.383	I (1)
Lnfa	Levels	.	-2.681	-1.782	-1.356	I (1)
	First diff	.	-2.718	-1.796	-1.363	I (1)

Note: GDP is the gross domestic product; REV is total revenue, PROF represents the profitability; TA is the total assets; and FA is the firm age. One/two asterisks denote significance at the 1%/10% level. 95% Critical Level for ADF

Cointegration Tests

Since gross domestic product, total revenue, profitability; total assets; and firm age contain unit root, this paper conducts a cointegration test suggested by Johansen to see whether these variables have a common stochastic trend. The results of cointegration tests (Table 4.2) show that no cointegration is found among the gross domestic product, total revenue, profitability; total assets; and firm age. That is the null hypotheses of no cointegration is accepted at the 5% level of significance. Table 4.2: Johansen Cointegration Tests

```
. vecrank lngdp lnrev lnprof lnta lnfa, trend(constant) max maximum lag
reduced to 1 because of collinearity
```

Johansen tests for cointegration

Trend: constant

Number of obs = 14

Sample: 2007 - 2020						Lags =	1		
maximum eigenvalue	statistic	value	0	5	trace	critical	rank	parms	5% LL
56.4909*	68.52				68.971666		.		
1	14	84.815541	0.89600	24.8031	47.21				
2	21	92.841618	0.68228	8.7509	29.68				
3	26	95.702669	0.33550	3.0288	15.41				
4	29	97.217092	0.19454	0.0000	3.76				
5	30	97.217092	0.00000						
5% maximum eigenvalue	statistic	value	0	5	max	critical	rank	parms	LL
31.6878	33.46				68.971666		.		
1	14	84.815541	0.89600	16.0522	27.07				
2	21	92.841618	0.68228	5.7221	20.97				
3	26	95.702669	0.33550	3.0288	14.07				
4	29	97.217092	0.19454	0.0000	3.76				
5	30	97.217092	0.00000						

Granger Causality Analysis

To analyse the statistical causality link between gross domestic product and the other variables, we

performed bivariate Granger Causality Tests. The Granger (1969) approach assesses whether past information on one variable helps in the prediction of the outcome of some other variables, given past information on the latter. It is important to note that the statement "x Granger causes y" does not imply that y is the effect or the result of x. Granger causality measures precedence and information content but does not by itself indicate causality in the more common use of the term.

Table 4.3 Granger causality Wald tests

Equation	Excluded	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
lnrdp	lnrev	102.85	2	0.000
lnrdp	lnprof	15.253	2	0.000
lnrdp	lnnta	69.12	2	0.000
lnrdp	lnfa	0	1	1.000
lnrdp	ALL	1091.8	7	0.000
lnrev	lnrdp	1.1709	2	0.557
lnrev	lnprof	3.5187	2	0.172
lnrev	lnnta	4.4582	2	0.108
lnrev	lnfa	0	1	1.000
lnrev	ALL	146.68	7	0.000
lnprof	lnrdp	5.1486	2	0.076
lnprof	lnrev	7.8443	2	0.020
lnprof	lnnta	8.5161	2	0.014

	lnprof	lnfa		0	1	1.000	
	lnprof	ALL		99.235	7	0.000	
-----+							
	lnta	lngdp		11.653	2	0.003	
	lnta	lnrev		7.5107	2	0.023	
	lnta	lnprof		10.312	2	0.006	
	lnta	lnfa		0	1	1.000	
	lnta	ALL		481.13	7	0.000	
-----+							
	lnfa	lngdp		3.5891	2	0.166	
	lnfa	lnrev		3.5446	2	0.170	
	lnfa	lnprof		2.918	2	0.232	
	lnfa	lnta		.04833	2	0.976	
	lnfa	ALL		11.494	8	0.175	
-----+							

Table 4.3, indicates the null hypothesis that firm size does not Granger cause economic growth and is rejected at the 5 per cent level of significance. This implies that there is a one-way causality going from firm size to economic growth. However, the null hypothesis that total assets does not Granger cause firm age is upheld at the 5 per cent level of significance. It is also observed from the table that between 2006 and 2020, lnrev, lnprof, lnta and lnfa granger cause lngdp. From the total revenue equation lngdp, lnprof, lnta and lnfa granger cause lnrev. While from the profitability equation lngdp, lnrev, lnta and lnfa granger cause lnprof. Total Asset equation shows that lngdp, lnrev, lnprof and lnfa granger cause lnfa. However, from firm age equation, lngdp, lnrev, lnprof and lnta does not granger cause lnfa which implies that useful information on firm age cannot be used to predict economic growth?

Lag Selection Criteria

VAR analysis was carried out for the time series data from lag1 to lag2 in order to obtain the minimum sequential modified LR test statistic (LR), Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Hannan-Quinn information Criterion (HQIC) and Schwarz Information Criterion (SBIC) (each test at 5% level). After a careful inspection of the lag selection criteria table 4.4, the result shows lags order at 2 by the selection criteria, the study preceded further tests with lags (2).

Table 4.2 Lag order selection

Selection-order criteria									
Sample: 2008 - 2020									
Number of obs = 13									
-----+									
lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC	
-----+									
0	57.9305				2.0e-10	-8.14316	-8.18782	-7.92587	
1	94.315	72.769	25	0.000	2.0e-11	-10.6638	-10.8872	-9.57741	
2	346.165	503.7*	25	0.000	2.6e-26*	-46.333*	-46.735*	-44.3774*	
-----+									
Endogenous: lngdp lnrev lnprof lnta lnfa									
Exogenous: _cons									

Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model

This paper is to find the macroeconomic impact of firm size on economic growth in Nigeria using the VAR analysis. The VAR estimation results are just the coefficient estimates for each equation in the VAR. The lag 2 VAR model result for the time series is presented below:

	lngdp	lnrev	lnprof	lnta	lnfa
lngdp (L1)	.9886552	.3220221	-.1957094	.0732005	0
	0.000	0.073	0.000	0.445	1.000
lngdp (L2)	.0301928	.3220221	-.1957094	.0732005	0
	0.755	0.000	0.944	0.000	
lnrev (L1)	-.3360672	.102171	.118393	.3481518	0
	0.473	0.840	0.407	0.197	1.000
lnrev (L2)	.2736313	-1.333372	.2878202	.5288088	0
	0.315	0.000	0.076	0.048	
lnprof (L1)	-1.629181	.8050316	-.0616955	-.2558407	0
	0.049	0.369	0.807	0.592	1.000
lnprof (L2)	.835597	-1.454738	.2317707	1.2271	0
	0.083	0.011	0.419	0.010	
lnta (L1)	.9713565	1.243435	.3551307	-.0719681	0
	0.165	0.100	0.096	0.858	1.000
lnta (L2)	1.001433	-.9672942	.7118547	-.0103992	0

	0.014	0.046	0.003	0.979	
lnfa (L1)	.037423 1	.0143123	.0087785	-.0017915	0
	0.125	0.587	0.238	0.899	1.000
lnfa (L2)	-.0222089	-.0292172	.0116247	.0018731	0

Revenue have a positive effect on gross domestic product in Nigeria at lag one and two, where the coefficient is statistically significant. Profitability and total asset also show some statistically significant on the revenue of the firm. The passed values of the all the variables have the mixed signs, for example, for total asset equation, the coefficient at lag two for gross domestic product turns out to positive and highly significant at 5%. For the gross domestic product equation, the first lag of profitability has a negative impact on gross domestic product at significant of 1% while the second lag of profitability does not have any significant impact on gross domestic product. It means that increase in firm profitability will increase gross domestic product on an average.

Robustness check

Dep. variable	t-statistics	Granger/Wald Test	Wald Coeff. Test	Decision:
<i>lngdp</i>	<i>lnrev_1and_2</i> : Significant <i>lnprof_1</i> : Significant <i>lnfa_2</i> : Significant	<i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnprof</i> : Significant <i>lnfa</i> : Significant	<i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnprof</i> : Significant <i>lnfa</i> : Significant	<i>lnrev</i> Ganger-causes <i>lngdp</i> <i>lnprof</i> Ganger-causes <i>lngdp</i> <i>lnfa</i> Ganger-causes <i>lngdp</i>
<i>lnrev</i>	<i>lnprof_2</i> : Significant <i>lnfa_2</i> : Significant			
<i>lnprof</i>	<i>lngdp_1and_2</i> : Significant <i>lnrev_2</i> : Significant <i>lnfa_2</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> : Significant <i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnfa</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> : Significant <i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnfa</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnprof</i> <i>lnrev</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnprof</i> <i>lnfa</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnprof</i>
<i>lnfa</i>	<i>lngdp_2</i> : Significant <i>lnrev_2</i> : Significant <i>lnprof_1 and_2</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> : Significant <i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnprof</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> : Significant <i>lnrev</i> : Significant <i>lnprof</i> : Significant	<i>lngdp</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnfa</i> <i>lnrev</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnfa</i> <i>lnprof</i> Ganger-causes <i>lnfa</i>
<i>lnfa</i>	<i>lnrev_2</i> : Significant			

Diagnostics test

Jarque-Bera test

75	
----	--

Equation	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
lngdp	0.590	2	0.74466
lnrev	0.814	2	0.66549
lnprof	1.060	2	0.58859
lnta	0.684	2	0.71048
lnfa	4.875	2	0.08738
ALL	8.023	10	0.62661

Eigenvalue stability condition

Eigenvalue	Modulus
.9588952	.958895
.1033724 + .7556806i	.762718
.1033724 - .7556806i	.762718
-.6838335	.683833
.4490551 + .2639435i	.520881
.4490551 - .2639435i	.520881
-.2113771 + .417302i	.467783
-.2113771 - .417302i	.467783
0	0
0	0

All the eigenvalues lie inside the unit circle. VAR satisfies stability condition.

Conclusion

In this study, we set out to empirically investigate the direction of causality between firm size and economic growth in Nigeria, using annual time series data from 2008 to 2020. Several statistical tools were employed to explore the relationship between firm size and economic growth. We started by examining the stochastic characteristics of each time series by testing their stationarity using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which revealed that firm size and economic growth was stationary at first difference. The essence of this test is to avoid spurious regression. Johansen cointegration tests shows no cointegration among the variables. However, Vector Auto Regression (VAR) analysis was carried out using optimal lag selection criteria 2 of the time series variables while the stability test shows that our model was stable. The result shows a unidirectional causality from *firm revenue* to *gross domestic product*; a unidirectional causality from *firm revenue* to *firm profitability*; and a unidirectional causality from *firm revenue* to *firm total asset*. In addition with a bi-directional causality from *firm profitability* to *gross domestic product* and vice versa; a bi-directional causality from *firm total asset* to *gross domestic product* and vice versa; and a bi-directional causality from *firm total asset* to *firm profitability* and vice versa.

versa. Since economic theory suggests that there is a positive relationship between firm size and economic growth, which is supported by our result that firm size granger causes gross domestic product, and gross domestic product granger causes firm size.

References

- Abubakar, A. [2021] An analysis on the impact of firm size on profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria; *Asian journal of Economics Business and Accounting*. 21 [3] 72-84 Akben-Seluck, E [2016]. Does firm age affect profitability? Evidence from Turkey. *International journal of economic sciences*. 3, 1-9
- Akinyei, O.J. and Olagunju, A[2013]. Effect of firm size on profitability; Evidence from Nigeria manufacturing sector. *Research.com*
- Amato,H. and Burson, T. E.[2007]. The effects of firm size on profit rates in financial service *Journal of economics and economic education research* 8 [1] pp 67-8 2.
- Audretsch, D.B and Elston, J.A. [2000]. Does firm size matter? Evidence on the impact of liquidity constraint on firms' investment behavior in Germany. *Hamburg institute of international economics*.
- Ayturk, Y. and Yanik, S. [2015]. Effect firm size on firms' performance and profitability. *Press academia*. 2017. 762-39 7205Pdf
- Chib, V.S. and Adriana, C. [2018]. Does financial perform matter?<http://www.researchgate.net>
- Dang ,C. Li, Z.F. and Yana, C. [2018] Measuring firm size in empirical corporate finance. *J. Bank Finance* 86; 159-176
- Dogan, M.[2013]. Does firm size affect profitability? Evidence from Turkey. *Research journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4[4] 53-59
- Ehi-Oshio, O. Adeyemi,A and Enofe, A [2013] Determinants of corporate profitability in developing economies. *European journal of business management* 5[16]
- Fazzari, S.M. Hubbard, G.R and Peterson, B.C [1988]. Investment strategy, Dividend policy and financial constraints of firms. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Gbafoorifard, M. Sheykh, B. Shakibae, M and Joshaghan, N.S.[2014] Assessing the relationship between firm size, age and financial performance in listed companies on Tehran stock exchange. *International journal of scientific management and development*.2 [4], 631-635.
- Hashmi, S.D. Gulzan,S and Naz,I. [2020]. Sensitivity of firm size measures to practices of corporate finance; evidence from BRICS. *Future Business Journal*.
- Hennesay, C.A. [2005]. Testing Q theory with financing functions. <https://doi.org> onson,B. [2007]. Does the size matter? The relationship between size and profitability of Icelandic firms. *Bitrost J. Social Science* 1; 43-55
- Kipsha, e.f. [2013] Impact of size and age on firm performance. Evidence from microfinance institutions in Tanzania. *Research journal of finance and accounting*, 4[5] 105-116
- Kitor, I. [2011]. Two definitions of firm size; Total sales and number of employees. *Researchgate*. Net Lee, J. [2009] Does firm size matter in firm performance? Evidence from U.S. public firms. *International journal Economics of Business*. 16[2]; 189-203
- Load, A. Segara, B.A and Teruel, M [2013] Family uncertainty and opacity . *Small Business Economics*, 4,0[4] 1035-1058.
- Loderer, C.F and Waelichli, U [2010]. Firm age and performance; SSRN working paper. Retrieved arch 01,2018 [de indirildi] from the world wild <https://paper.ssm.com>
- Mazunder, D [1991] Import-substituting industrialization and protection of the small-scale. The Indian experience in the textile industry. *World development*, 19[9] 1197-1213
- Mule, R.K. Mukras, M.S and Nzioka, O.M [2015]. Corporate size, profitability and market value. An econometric panel analysis of listed firms in Kenya. *European scientific journal*; 11 [13] 376-396.
- Niresh, J.A. and Velnapy, T. [2014] Firm size and profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Sri- Lanka. *International journal of business and management*. 9[4] 57-64

- Osunsan, O.K Nowak, J. Mabonga, E. Pule, S. Kibirige, A.R and Baliruno, J.B [2015]. Firm age and Performance in Kampala, Uganda. A selection of small business enterprises; International journal of Academic Research in Business and social sciences 5[4]364-374
- Papadogonas, T. A.[2007]. The financial performance of large and small firms. Evidence from Greece . International journal of financial management 2[1/2]; 14-20
- Pattitoni, P. Petracci, B and Spisni, M [2014]. Determinants of profitability in the E.U-15 area. Applied financial economics. 24 [11], 763-775. .
- Pervan, M and Visic, T. [2012]. Influence of firm size on its business success. Croatian operational research review 3[1] 213-223
- Prasetyantoko,A. and Parono, R. [2009] Does firm size matter? An empirical study of firm performance in Indonesia. International Research Journal of BusinessStudies 2[2] 87-97
- Rajesh Pathak in Head lock –Pierce theory [2020] Earnings quality and quality pay-out policy linkage; An Indian context. The North American Journal of Economics and finance vol.[5]
- Serrasqueiro, Z.S. Nunes, P.M [2008]. Performance and size. Empirical evidence from Portuguese S.M.Es. Small Business Economics. 3 [2]; 195-217
- Sugosha,M.J and Artini, L.G.S. [2020] The role of profitability in mediating company ownership structure and size of firm value in the pharmaceutical industry inIndonesia. International research journal of management. [http//doi.org](http://doi.org). .
- Talha, A. Muhammed, U.F. Hamza, A and Abdul, A [2021]. The impact of firm size on profitability; a study on the top 10 cement companies of Pakistan. Researchgate.net
- Thesai, A [2012]. The effect of firm size on corporate performance [http//thesai.org](http://thesai.org)